

Archiving, sharing and discussing research data on Eastern Europe, South Caucasus and Central Asia

Data Review

Data Citation

Nathalie Rathkamp (2025): Review of Pennsylvania State University (1998): The Computational Event Data System (published on Discuss Data), v. 1.0, Discuss Data, <https://doi.org/10.48320/E77741EC-9BB8-4F86-81E4-5512C395454A>

Abstract

The Computational Event Data System (KEDS) compiles political event data using automated coding of English-language news reports. The project was originally founded by the University of Kansas under the name 'Kansas Event Data System (KEDS)', and then moved to the Department of Political Science of the Pennsylvania State University. The project covers the time-period from May 1989 to July 1999 focusing on the Middle East, Balkans, and West Africa, while also offering datasets for other regions (1). This data review will focus on the Central Asia dataset. Of the 38.000+ total entries in this dataset, there are 6.200+ events listed for the countries of Eastern Europe, South Caucasus and Central Asia covered by Discuss Data. As of summer 2024, the data collection seems to have concluded (3). The data review contains a link leading to the official Computational Event Data System website from which both the dataset and additional information are available as a free download. However, please note that not all browsers are able to open the download link.

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Data Review - The Computational Event Data System

The Computational Event Data System (KEDS) compiles political event data using automated coding of English-language news reports. The project was originally founded by the University of Kansas under the name 'Kansas Event Data System (KEDS)', and then moved to the Department of Political Science of the Pennsylvania State University. The project covers the time-period from May 1989 to July 1999 focusing on the Middle East, Balkans, and West Africa, while also offering datasets for other regions (1). This data review will focus on the Central Asia dataset.

KEDS focuses on three major research areas. The first of which is the development of software for the machine-coding of the collected political event data. This technological approach replaced the labor-intensive and error-prone process of human coding with the advantages of inexpensive, transparent and reproducible automated coding (2).

The second focus lies within the production of the KEDS event data itself. During the coding of the Central Asia dataset news reports from the Reuters Business Briefing service were evaluated using the above mentioned developed automated coding programs. During evaluation the World Events Interaction Survey (WEIS) event coding scheme was utilized. The WEIS coding scheme includes the variables: date, source, target, WEIS code and type of action (2). When downloading the data, additional dictionaries used for coding will be downloaded simultaneously. These include (a) a dictionary that lists possible actors and explains their abbreviations used within the dataset ("CASIA.ACTORs"), (b) a dictionary that explains the definition of the listed WEIS codes ("CASIA.CLASSES"), and (c) a dictionary that lists the possible types of actions ("CASIA.VERBS"). On top of that an MS-Excel spreadsheet containing the number of events and total Goldstein scores aggregated by month for each country is also included.

The third research focus of KEDS is the development of early warning methods that predict incoming political change preemptively. So far KEDS has experimented with various methods towards this end. These methods include: factor analysis, discriminant analysis, an assortment of clustering algorithms and hidden Markov models (2).

Discuss Data relevant country coverage:

Country	Number of Entries
Armenia	1000(+)
Azerbaijan	1000(+)
Belarus	238
Georgia	450

Kazakhstan	1000(+)
Kyrgyzstan	751
Lithuania	11
Russia	1000(+)
Tajikistan	1000(+)
Turkmenistan	153
Ukraine	441
Uzbekistan	1000(+)

Sources:

- (1) The Computational Event Data System. 2013.
<https://parusanalytics.com/eventdata/index.html>. Last accessed 19.09.2024.
- (2) The Computational Event Data Project.
<https://parusanalytics.com/eventdata/home.dir/project.html>. Last accessed 19.09.2024.
- (3) Central Asia Data Set, 1989-199. 1999.
<https://parusanalytics.com/eventdata/data.dir/casia.html>. Last accessed 19.09.2024.